

Some Elementary Properties of Neutrosophic Integers

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Abstract: In this paper, we firstly defined a relation in the set of neutrosophic integers $Z[I]$ and proved that this relation is an equivalence relation. Thus we obtained a partition of $Z[I]$. Secondly we investigated the ordering relation in $Z[I]$ and we have seen that $Z[I]$ is not a totally ordered set. We also gave some relations of positive and negative neutrosophic integers and ordering in $Z[I]$. In the last part of the paper, we introduced the factorial of a positive neutrosophic integer.

Keywords: Neutrosophic integers; ordering in neutrosophic integers; factorial of a neutrosophic integer.

1. Introduction

Neutrosophy concept is presented by Smarandache to deal with indeterminacy in nature and science [1]. Neutrosophy has a lot of important applications in many fields and hundreds of studies have been done in these fields. One of these fields is neutrosophic number theory. Neutrosophic number theory is a mathematical way to deal with the properties of neutrosophic integers. Neutrosophic number theory was introduced in [2]. In [2], some properties of neutrosophic integers were introduced as division theorem, the form of primes in $Z[I]$.

In this study, it is obtained a partition of the set $Z[I]$ by an equivalence relation. Then it is investigated the ordering relation in $Z[I]$ and have seen that $Z[I]$ is not a totally ordered set, also given some relations of positive and negative neutrosophic integers and ordering in $Z[I]$. In the last part of the paper, we introduced the factorial of a positive neutrosophic integer.

2. Preliminaries

In the following, we give some elementary definitions and results for emphasis.

Definition 2.1 [3] Let $(R; +, \cdot)$ be a ring and I be an indeterminate element which satisfies $I^2 = I$. The set $R[I] = \{a + bI : a, b \in R\}$ is called a neutrosophic ring generated by I and R under the binary operations of R .

For example; $Z[I] = \{a + bI : a, b \in Z\}$ is a neutrosophic ring generated by I and Z where Z is integers ring. $Z[I]$ is called neutrosophic integers ring.

Definition 2.2 [4] Let $R[I] = \{a + bI : a, b \in R\}$ be the field of neutrosophic real numbers where R is the field of real numbers. For $a + bI, c + dI \in R[I]$,

$$a + bI \leq c + dI \Leftrightarrow a \leq c, a + b \leq c + d.$$

Theorem 2.1 [4] The relation defined in Definition 2.2 is a partial order relation.

According to Definition 2.2, we are able to define positive neutrosophic real numbers as follows:

$$a + bI \geq 0 \Leftrightarrow a \geq 0, a + b \geq 0.$$

3. Ordering in Neutrosophic Integers

Definition 3.1 Let $a + bI, c + dI \in Z[I]$. If $a + b = c + d$, then the neutrosophic integers $a + bI$ and $c + dI$ are said to be equivalent and denoted by $a + bI \square c + dI$. Then we write this with symbolically:

$$a + bI \square c + dI \Leftrightarrow a + b = c + d.$$

Example 3.1 Since $-1 + 1 = 2 - 2$, we have $-1 + I \square 2 - 2I$ and since $2 + 3 \neq 1 + 2$, we have $2 + 3I$ is not equivalent to $1 + 2I$.

Theorem 3.1 The relation " $\square$ " is an equivalence relation.

Proof. It can be proved easily.

The relation " $\square$ " separates the set $Z[I]$ into equivalence classes. The equivalence class of any $a + bI \in Z[I]$ denoted by $\overline{a + bI}$ and

$$\overline{a + bI} = \{x + yI : x + yI \in Z[I], x + yI \square a + bI\}.$$

If we match $a + bI \in Z[I]$ to the point (a, b) on the cartesian plane, then the equivalence class $\overline{a + bI}$ is the set of the points (x, y) where $x, y \in Z$ on the line $x + y = a + b$.

Example 3.2

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{0 + 0I} &= \{x + yI : x + yI \in Z[I], x + yI \square 0 + 0I\} \\ &= \{x + yI : x, y \in Z, x + y = 0\} \\ &= \{\dots, -2 + 2I, -1 + I, 0 + 0I, 1 - I, 2 - 2I, \dots\}. \end{aligned}$$

$\overline{0 + 0I} = \bar{0}$ is the set of the points (x, y) where $x, y \in Z$ on the line $x + y = 0$.

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{1 + 0I} &= \{x + yI : x + yI \in Z[I], x + yI \square 1 + 0I\} \\ &= \{x + yI : x, y \in Z, x + y = 1\} \\ &= \{\dots, -2 + 3I, -1 + 2I, 0 + I, 1 - 0I, 2 - I, \dots\}. \end{aligned}$$

$\overline{1 + 0I} = \bar{1}$ is the set of the points (x, y) where $x, y \in Z$ on the line $x + y = 1$.

If we define the set $D = \{\overline{a + bI} : a + bI \in Z[I]\}$, then $D = \{\dots, \bar{-2}, \bar{-1}, \bar{0}, \bar{1}, \bar{2}, \dots\} = \{\bar{m} : m \in Z\}$. For $m, n \in Z$ and $m \neq n$, we see that $\bar{m} \cap \bar{n} = \emptyset$ and $\bigcup_{m \in Z} \bar{m} = Z[I]$. Then it is also obvious that the set D is a partition of $Z[I]$.

Definition 2.2 is valid for $Z[I]$. Let's rewrite it for topic integrity:

Definition 3.2 Let $a + bI, c + dI \in Z[I]$. If $a \leq c$ and $a + b \leq c + d$, we say that the neutrosophic integer $a + bI$ is less than or equal to $c + dI$ and denoted by $a + bI \leq c + dI$. Shortly, we write:

$$a + bI \leq c + dI \Leftrightarrow a \leq c, a + b \leq c + d.$$

Note that the relation " $\leq$ " is a partially ordering relation. Hence the set $Z[I]$ is a partially ordered set according to the relation " $\leq$ " but it is not a totally ordered set. Because, every element of $Z[I]$ can not be compared. For example; $1-2I$ and $-1+3I$ are incomparable. That is, $1-2I \not\leq -1+3I$ and $-1+3I \not\leq 1-2I$.

Example 3.3 The set of $x+yI \in Z[I]$ which satisfy $1+I \leq x+yI$ on the cartesian plane is drawn below:

Figure 1. The set of $x+yI \in Z[I]$ which satisfy $1+I \leq x+yI$ on the cartesian plane.

Corollary 2.1 Let $a+bI \in Z[I]$.

- i) $a+bI \geq 0 \Leftrightarrow a \geq 0$ and $a+b \geq 0$,
- ii) $a+bI \leq 0 \Leftrightarrow a \leq 0$ and $a+b \leq 0$.

Proof. The first relation was given in [4]. (i) and (ii) can be proven using the Definition 3.2.

If we match $a+bI \in Z[I]$ to the point (a,b) on the cartesian plane, we can show the regions of positive and negative neutrosophic integers:

Figure 2. Positive and negative neutrosophic integers on cartesian plane.

We denote the set of positive neutrosophic integers by $Z[I]^+$. We know that the set $Z[I]^+$ is not totally ordered set. We can see that $1 \leq 1+I \leq 2$ and $1 \leq 2-I \leq 2$ but $1+I$ and $2-I$ are incomparable. $0+0I$ is the smallest element of the set $Z[I]^+ \cup \{0+0I\}$. But the set $Z[I]^+$ has not smallest element.

The subsemilattice of the set $Z[I]^+ \cup \{0+0I\}$ is given the following figure:

Figure 3. The subsemilattice of the set $Z[I]^+ \cup \{0+0I\}$.

Theorem 3.2 Let $x = a+bI, y = c+dI \in Z[I]$. Then $x \leq y$ if and only if there exists an $u \in Z[I]$ such that $u \geq 0$ and $x+u = y$.

Proof. Suppose that there exists an $u \in Z[I]$ such that $u \geq 0$ and $x+u = y$. Then, if $u = u_1 + u_2I$, we get $u_1 \geq 0$ and $u_1 + u_2 \geq 0$. Also since $x+u = y$, we have $a+bI + u_1 + u_2I = c+dI$. So $a+u_1 = c$ and $b+u_2 = d$ or $u_1 = c-a$ and $u_2 = d-b$. Since $u_1 \geq 0$, we get $c-a \geq 0$ or $a \leq c$. Also since $u_1 + u_2 \geq 0$, we have $c-a+d-b \geq 0$ or $a+b \leq c+d$. Hence since $a \leq c$ and $a+b \leq c+d$, we see that $x \leq y$. Conversely, let $x \leq y$. Then $a+b \leq c+d$. Hence we have $a \leq c$ and $a+b \leq c+d$ in Z . Then if we say $c-a = u_1$ and $d-b = u_2$, we see that $u_1 \geq 0$ and $u_1 + u_2 \geq 0$. Then we have $u = u_1 + u_2I \in Z[I]$ and $u \geq 0$.

$$\begin{aligned} x+u &= a+bI + u_1 + u_2I \\ &= a+bI + c-a + (d-b)I \\ &= c+dI \\ &= y. \end{aligned}$$

Example 3.4 We know that $-3+2I \leq 2+I$. Then $-3+2I + 5-I = 2+I$ and $5-I \geq 0$.

Theorem 3.3 Let $x = x_1 + x_2I, y = y_1 + y_2I, z = z_1 + z_2I$ and $u = u_1 + u_2I \in Z[I]$. Then

- (i) $x \leq y \Leftrightarrow x+z \leq y+z$,
- (ii) $x \leq y$ and $z \leq u \Rightarrow x+z \leq y+u$,
- (iii) $x \leq y$ and $z \geq 0 \Rightarrow xz \leq yz$,

(iv) $x \leq y$ and $z \leq 0 \Rightarrow xz \geq yz$,

Proof. (i) Since $x+z = x_1+z_1+(x_2+z_2)I$ and $y+z = y_1+z_1+(y_2+z_2)I$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} x \leq y &\Leftrightarrow x_1+x_2I \leq y_1+y_2I \\ &\Leftrightarrow x_1 \leq y_1 \text{ and } x_1+x_2 \leq y_1+y_2 \text{ in } Z \\ &\Leftrightarrow x_1+z_1 \leq y_1+z_1 \text{ and } x_1+x_2+z_1+z_2 \leq y_1+y_2+z_1+z_2 \text{ for } z_1, z_2 \in Z \\ &\Leftrightarrow x_1+z_1+(x_2+z_2)I \leq y_1+z_1+(y_2+z_2)I \\ &\Leftrightarrow x+z \leq y+z. \end{aligned}$$

(ii) Since $x+z = x_1+z_1+(x_2+z_2)I$ and $y+z = y_1+u_1+(y_2+u_2)I$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} x \leq y \text{ and } z \leq u &\Rightarrow x_1+x_2I \leq y_1+y_2I \text{ and } z_1+z_2I \leq u_1+u_2I \\ &\Rightarrow x_1 \leq y_1, x_1+x_2 \leq y_1+y_2, z_1 \leq u_1 \text{ and } z_1+z_2 \leq u_1+u_2 \\ &\Rightarrow x_1+z_1 \leq y_1+u_1, x_1+x_2+z_1+z_2 \leq y_1+y_2+u_1+u_2 \\ &\Rightarrow x_1+z_1+(x_2+z_2)I \leq y_1+u_1+(y_2+u_2)I \\ &\Rightarrow x+z \leq y+u. \end{aligned}$$

(iii) Let $z = z_1+z_2I \geq 0$. Then $z_1 \geq 0$ and $z_1+z_2 \geq 0$. Since $xz = x_1z_1+(x_1z_2+x_2z_1+x_2z_2)I$ and $yz = y_1z_1+(y_1z_2+y_2z_1+y_2z_2)I$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} x \leq y &\Leftrightarrow x_1+x_2I \leq y_1+y_2I \\ &\Leftrightarrow x_1 \leq y_1, x_1+x_2 \leq y_1+y_2 \\ &\Leftrightarrow x_1z_1 \leq y_1z_1 \text{ and } (x_1+x_2)(z_1+z_2) \leq (y_1+y_2)(z_1+z_2) \\ &\Leftrightarrow x_1z_1 \leq y_1z_1 \text{ and } x_1z_1+x_1z_2+x_2z_1+x_2z_2 \leq y_1z_1+y_1z_2+y_2z_1+y_2z_2 \\ &\Leftrightarrow x_1z_1+(x_1z_2+x_2z_1+x_2z_2)I \leq y_1z_1+(y_1z_2+y_2z_1+y_2z_2)I \\ &\Leftrightarrow xz \leq yz. \end{aligned}$$

iv) Let $z = z_1+z_2I \leq 0$. Then $z_1 \leq 0$ and $z_1+z_2 \leq 0$. Since $xz = x_1z_1+(x_1z_2+x_2z_1+x_2z_2)I$ and $yz = y_1z_1+(y_1z_2+y_2z_1+y_2z_2)I$, we have,

$$\begin{aligned} x \leq y &\Leftrightarrow x_1+x_2I \leq y_1+y_2I \\ &\Leftrightarrow x_1 \leq y_1, x_1+x_2 \leq y_1+y_2 \\ &\Leftrightarrow x_1z_1 \geq y_1z_1 \text{ and } (x_1+x_2)(z_1+z_2) \geq (y_1+y_2)(z_1+z_2) \\ &\Leftrightarrow x_1z_1 \geq y_1z_1 \text{ and } x_1z_1+x_1z_2+x_2z_1+x_2z_2 \geq y_1z_1+y_1z_2+y_2z_1+y_2z_2 \\ &\Leftrightarrow x_1z_1+(x_1z_2+x_2z_1+x_2z_2)I \geq y_1z_1+(y_1z_2+y_2z_1+y_2z_2)I \\ &\Leftrightarrow xz \geq yz. \end{aligned}$$

4. Factorial of a Positive Neutrosophic Number

It is known that $n! = n.(n-1)...2.1$ for a $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ and $0! = 1$. This is the product of all integers less than or equal to n on the positive real axis of the coordinate system.

Now we want to extend the factorial concept in Z to $Z[I]$. For $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, we have $n = n+0I \in Z[I]$. Then we can write $(n+0I)! = (n+0I).(n-1+0I)...(2+0I).(1+0I)$. The numbers $n+0I, n-1+0I, \dots, 2+0I, 1+0I$ are some positive neutrosophic integers less than or equal to $n+0I$. If we match these numbers to the points $(n,0), (n-1,0), \dots, (2,0), (1,0)$, we see that they are on the half line $y=0, x=0$.

Now we take $5+5I \in Z[I]$. Then the numbers $5+5I, 4+4I, 3+3I, 2+2I, 1+I$ are some positive neutrosophic integers less than or equal to $5+5I$. If we match these numbers to the points

(5,5),(4,4),(3,3),(2,2),(1,1) , we see that they are on the half line $y = x$. We can write

$$\begin{aligned} (5+5I)! &= (5+5I)(4+4I)(3+3I)(2+2I)(1+I) \\ &= 5.4.3.2.1.(1+I)^5 \\ &= 5!(1+I)^5 \end{aligned}$$

Now we construct $(12+16I)!$ similarly. The points $(12,16),(9,12),(6,8),(3,4)$ are on the half line

$y = \frac{16}{12}x = \frac{4}{3}x$. The corresponding neutrosophic integers $12+16I, 9+12I, 6+8I, 3+4I$ are less than

or equal to $12+16I$. So we can write

$$\begin{aligned} (12+16I)! &= (12+16I)(9+12I)(6+8I)(3+4I) \\ &= 4.3.2.1.(3+4I)^4 \\ &= 4!(3+4I)^4 \end{aligned}$$

Now we are ready to define the factorial of a positive neutrosophic integer:

Definition 4.1 Let $a + bI \in Z[I]$. Then

$$(a + bI)! = d! \left(\frac{a}{d} + \frac{b}{d}I \right)^d$$

where $d = \gcd\{a, b\}$ ($\gcd$:greatest common divisor).

Example 4.1

i) $5! = (5+0I)! = 5! \left(\frac{5}{5} + \frac{0}{5}I \right)^5 = 5!+0I$ since $\gcd\{5,0\} = 5$.

ii) $(0+5I)! = 5! \left(\frac{0}{5} + \frac{5}{5}I \right)^5 = 0+5!I$ since $\gcd\{0,5\} = 5$.

iii) $(9-3I)! = 3! \left(\frac{9}{3} - \frac{3}{3}I \right)^3 = 3!(3-I)^3$ since $\gcd\{9,-3\} = 3$.

The following Theorem and its proof were given for the neutrosophic n square matrices in [5, Theorem 3.6].

Theorem 4.1 Let $a + bI \in Z[I]$. Then,

$$(a + bI)^n = a^n + ((a + b)^n - a^n)I$$

for $n \in Z^+$.

Proof. We use induction on n . For $n=1$, the above equality is true. Suppose that the claim is true for

$n-1$. That is, $(a + bI)^{n-1} = a^{n-1} + ((a + b)^{n-1} - a^{n-1})I$. Then we have

$$\begin{aligned} (a + bI)^n &= (a + bI)^{n-1}(a + bI) \\ &= \left(a^{n-1} + ((a + b)^{n-1} - a^{n-1})I \right) (a + bI) \\ &= a^n + \left(a^{n-1}b + (a + b)^{n-1}a - a^n + (a + b)^{n-1}b - a^{n-1}b \right) I \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= a^n + ((a+b)^{n-1}(a+b) - a^n)I \\
&= a^n + ((a+b)^n - a^n)I
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore Theorem is true.

Corollary 4.1 Let $a + bI \in \mathbb{Z}[I]^+$. Then

$$(a + bI)! = d! \left\{ \left(\frac{a}{d} \right)^d + \left[\left(\frac{a}{d} + \frac{b}{d} \right)^d - \left(\frac{a}{d} \right)^d \right] I \right\}$$

where $d = \gcd\{a, b\}$.

Proof. It is clear by Definition 4.1 and Theorem 4.1.

5. Conclusions

In this paper, it is obtained a partition of the set $\mathbb{Z}[I]$ by an equivalence relation. Then, it is investigated the ordering relation in $\mathbb{Z}[I]$ and have seen that $\mathbb{Z}[I]$ is not a totally ordered set, also given some relations of positive and negative neutrosophic integers and ordering in $\mathbb{Z}[I]$. In the last part of the paper, we introduced the factorial of a positive neutrosophic integer. In our future studies, we intend to continue to examine the properties of $\mathbb{Z}[I]$.

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